

**PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS OF
"ADMINISTRATION" AND "SCHOOL PRINCIPAL"
REFLECTED THROUGH METAPHORSⁱ**

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Abstract:

This study aims to present pre-service teachers' perceptions of "administration" and "school principal" reflected through metaphors; a purpose based on the fact that although they are trained in educational administration with only one course at university, pre-service teachers who are trained in the faculties of education constitute the group with the highest potential for becoming educational administrators in Turkish education system. The study group is the 4th grade (senior) university students who were chosen by means of criterion sampling method and who study at Preschool Teaching, Primary School Teaching, Social Sciences Teaching, Science Teaching, Music Teaching, Art Teaching, Psychological Counseling and Guidance programs at Adnan Menderes University. The criteria were the students' year of education and the course of Turkish Education System and School Management they take during their higher education. In this study which is based on phenomenology research design, a written form was used as the data collection tool aiming the perception of pre-service students for administration and school principal through metaphors. After the content analysis of the data gathered through written forms, it has been found out that pre-service students have mostly positive perceptions of administration and school principal concepts and administration is perceived to a more authoritarian structure while school principal and administration are considered equal in terms of responsibility.

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1. Introduction

Educational management as a field of expertise differs from business management and public administration in terms of purpose and function. What creates such a difference is the distinctive nature of education. And what makes educational administration a unique field is the distinctiveness of education as a social institution (Aydın, 2015: 155). The quality of educational purpose requires an internal and constant co-operation and collaboration between education and other social institutions. This is an operational necessity and gives educational administration a unique quality (Aydın, 2015:156).

When educational administration is viewed within Turkish education system, it is seen that training activities and several educational institutions were united under the Law of the Unity of Education No. 430 (passed on March 3rd, 1924) after the proclamation Turkish Republic. The then governments tried to reform the structure of central and provincial organizations in order to realize the unity of education in accordance with the law (Başaran, 1993:16). Although in 1924 John Dewey proposed in his report on Turkish education system that courses and programs were opened to train school administrators, there was hardly a considerable development (Cemaloğlu, 2005). In 1928, the Department of Pedagogy was founded under Gazi Institute of Education in order to provide administrators, inspectors, and teachers for the new educational organizations (Örücü ve Şimşek, 2011). Primary school teachers who were experienced, accomplished and willing to be administrators and inspectors were admitted to the department of pedagogy after written exams and interviews. During their time in the department, these teachers were trained in teaching profession, administration, and inspection. Until 1970, 90% of those who worked as administrators in central and provincial organizations had graduated from the Department of Pedagogy (Balci, 2008; Balci ve Apaydın, 2009)

The founding of TODAIE (Public Administration Institute for Turkey and Middle East) in 1956 indicates that administration in education is considered a whole different area. The MEHTAP (Central Government Organization Research Project) report, prepared in 1962, underlines the necessity of treating educational management as a special field of expertise and training administrators, and proposes opening new departments at universities. In the academic year of 1979-1980 programs of specialization were opened. The first faculty of education in Turkey is Ankara University Faculty of Education which opened in the academic year of 1965-1966. In 1982, the faculty was renamed as Faculty of Educational Sciences and under the

Department of Educational Administration, Inspection, Economy, and Planning, sub-departments of Educational Administration and Inspection, Educational Economy and Planning were opened. The opening of the Faculty of Education in Ankara University was followed by Gazi University, Hacettepe University, İstanbul University, 9 Eylül University, Yüzüncü Yıl University, and Abant İzzet Baysal University. The faculties of education at these universities provided administrators, inspectors, and specialists for Turkish education system. However, the Council of Higher Education closed the abovementioned departments in 1997 and the education continues exclusively at postgraduate level (Cemaloğlu, 2005).

Until 1998, the main criteria for assigning administrators to schools would be the principle of merit. A by-law in 1998 established that the school administrators could be commissioned after attending a 120-hour preparatory program and scoring minimum 70 points in a follow-up exam. The by-laws regulating the rules for assigning administrators have changed several times since 2003. Sometimes a single by-law changed more than once in one year. The June 2014 by-law, while maintaining the previous general conditions, stipulated that school administrators could continue their duty, after four years of service, in an institution on the basis of points obtained from internal and external stakeholders (Official Gazette, 2014). According to the most recent by-law ("Regulation on Commissioning Administrators to Educational Institutions of Ministry of National Education" dated October 6, 2015 and numbered 29494), head assistants and deputy principals are commissioned on the basis of written exam, while principals are commissioned on the basis of managerial appraisal and interview scores (Official Gazette, 2015).

In Turkey, bachelor programs for training school administrators are unavailable. Pre-service teachers take the course titled "Turkish Education System and School Administration" during their third or fourth year at university. There is no additional training in this area at bachelor level. Master and doctorate training which is carried out in the institutes of education and social sciences train specialists in the programs of Educational Administration, Educational Administration and Inspection, Educational Management and Inspection Planning and Economy.

In this study, it is aimed to investigate how pre-service teachers perceive the concepts of "school principal" and "administration" by means of the concept of metaphor. Metaphors can be used to re-define realities and stimulate re-conceptualization of problems as metaphors affect the ways we perceive conditions and incidents (Cerit, 2008; Goldstein, 2005). People transfer images, concepts, and terminology to an unknown or lesser known area by means of metaphors. Metaphors are useful for understanding and explaining a new phenomenon because they transfer

the meaning of a well-known situation to an unknown situation. Therefore, learning becomes easier with metaphors. Also, metaphors are way thinking and seeing (Cerit 2008; Morgan, 1998: 14).

2. The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to present pre-service teachers' perceptions of "administration" and "school principal" reflected through metaphors; a purpose based on the fact that although they are trained in educational administration with only one course at university, pre-service teachers who are trained in the faculties of education constitute the group with the highest potential for becoming educational administrators in Turkish education system. The study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. Which metaphors do pre-service teachers use to define the concept of "administration"?
2. Which metaphors do pre-service teachers use to define the concept of "school principal"?
3. Under what conceptual categories can pre-service teachers' metaphors of "administration" and "school principal" be put?

3. Method

3.1 Research Model

This qualitative study, which aims to present pre-service teachers' perceptions of "administration" and "school principal" reflected through metaphors, was carried out by means of metaphoric data analysis. The study is based on phenomenology research design. Phenomenological research design focuses on familiar but partly-understood, hence lesser known, phenomena. Phenomena might appear in the form of incidents, experience, perceptions, inclinations, concepts, and conditions (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008). Therefore, phenomenological design was used in this study because it examines thoroughly the meanings attributed to the concepts of "administration" and "school principal" by pre-service teachers.

3.2 Target Population

The target population of the research is made up of 4th grade (senior) university students who were chosen by means of criterion sampling method and who study at Preschool Teaching, Primary School Teaching, Social Sciences Teaching, Science Teaching, Music Teaching, Art Teaching, Psychological Counseling and Guidance

programs at Adnan Menderes University. The criteria were the students' year of education and the course of Turkish Education System and School Management they take during their higher education.

All the participants who were chosen by means of criterion sampling method and indicated in Table 1 are 4th grade (senior) students. The percentages of participation by bachelor programs is as follows: 12,7% Preschool Teaching, 27,4% Psychological Counseling and Guidance, 10,2% Computer Education and Instructional Technology, 15,2% Preschool Teaching, 8,5% Science Teaching, 16,2% Social Sciences Teaching, and 9,6% Art Teaching.

Table 1: Characteristics of Participants

Department	f	%
Primary School Teaching	25	12,7
Psychological Counseling and Guidance	54	27,4
Computer Education and Instructional Technology	20	10,2
Preschool Teaching	30	15,2
Science Teaching	17	8,6
Social Sciences Teaching	32	16,2
Art Teaching	19	9,6
Total	197	100,0

As it can be seen in Table 1, 197 participants took part in the research, but 23 questionnaire forms for "administration" metaphor and 16 questionnaire forms for "school principal" metaphor were excluded as they contained missing information. Ultimately, answers about administration metaphor from 174 pre-service teachers and school principal metaphor from 181 were evaluated and analyzed.

3.3 Data Collection Tool

In order to determine the cognitive images of "administration" and "school principal" created by pre-service teachers, the participants were asked to fill in the forms with the questions "Administration is like because....." and "School Principal is like because....." The participants were informed about the study and were asked to fill in the forms in 20 minutes.

3.4 Data Analysis

The data was analyzed through content analysis and then the metaphors were put under conceptual categories. For the analysis of the metaphors mentioned by pre-service teachers, a five-stage process which contained the following stages was used: 1)

identification 2) classification 3) generating categories 4) validity and reliability check 5) frequency and interpretation (Saban, Koçbeker ve Saban, 2006).

1. Identification: In this first stage, metaphors and sentences mentioned by pre-service teachers were checked. Then a list of metaphors was created. The metaphors written on the questionnaire forms by each participant were encoded. Forms with missing information were detected.
2. Classification: Questionnaire forms filled in by the participants were examined and the metaphors, along with the explanations, were reviewed. The reasons for creating particular metaphors were examined and the subject, source, and metaphor-source relation of each metaphor was taken into consideration for the analysis.
3. Generating categories: During this stage the reasons for "school principal" and "administration" metaphors were examined. And then conceptual categories were generated by means of content analysis. The results of the analysis indicated that 197 pre-service teachers came up with 174 metaphors for the concept of "administration" and these metaphors could be classified under 11 categories; 133 metaphors for the concept of "school principal" and these metaphors could be classified under 15 categories.
4. Validity and reliability: The researcher paid attention to not providing examples and guidance in order to preserve the originality of participants' views. Since credibility and transmissibility is significant for validity, the metaphors created by the participants were listed directly in the study and the interpretation of the findings was based on this list. Additionally, data analysis process was explained in detail for validity. For reliability, each researcher created an individual classification system and the systems were tested for reliability by using Miles and Huberman (1994) formula ($\text{Reliability} = \frac{\text{consensus}}{\text{consensus} + \text{divergence}}$). The calculations showed that the percentage of consensus among the researchers was 90%.
5. Frequency and interpretation: The researcher calculated the number and percentage of pre-service teachers that corresponded to each metaphor and category. The findings were presented in tables and interpreted.

3.5 Results

The results of the study, which investigated how pre-service teachers studying at Adnan Menderes University, Faculty of Education perceive the concepts of "school principal" and "administration" through metaphors, were classified under two titles – "Administration" and "School Principal."

3.6 "Administration" Metaphors Created by Pre-service Teachers

The metaphors created by Adnan Menderes University, Faculty of Education senior students as a response to the question "Administration is like.....because....." and the categories of metaphors are presented below in Table 2.

Table 2: Administration Metaphors and Categories

Category	Metaphor	f
Administration as a significant structure	Brain (4), Tree (2), Human (2), Roots of a tree (1), Mother (1), Rail system under a building (1), Wheel (1), Roof (1), Doctor (1), Closet (1), Plum pit (1), Power (1), Foundation of everything (1), Our muscles (1), King (1), Maestro(1), Pyramid (1), Water (1)	23
Administration as hierarchical unity and integrity	Domino (2), Machine (2), Octopus (1), Computer (1), Fridge (1), Wheel (1), Natural cycle (1), Football match (1), Cell (1), Interlocking circles (1), Human body (1), Building (1), Choir (1), User's manual (1), Musical tune (1), Puzzle (1), Clock (1), Clock gears (1), Sudoku (1), Theatre play (1), Pieces of puzzle (1), Rubik's cube (1)	24
Administration as a structure that requires skills and training	Driving (1), Brain (1), A work of literature (1), Building skyscrapers (1), Power (1), Amusement park (1), Stairs (1), Marketing (1), Art (1), Magic hand (1)	10
Administration as a structure that solves problems	Family (1), Householder (1), Public order (1), Horse riding (1), Garden (1), Step (1), Crossword puzzle (1), China (1), Spinning wheel (1), Factory (1), Protection (1), Box (1), Labyrinth (1), Puzzle (1), Umbrella (1), Treatment (1), Traffic (1), Rubik's cube (1)	18
Administration as an authoritarian structure	Power (2), Ankara (1), Imposition (1), Dictator (1), Steering wheel (1), Conventional teacher (1), Door (1), Belt (1), Air conditioner (1), Pillars that support institutions (1), Window (1), Glue (1)	13
Administration as a guiding structure	Mother (2), Core (2), Brain (1), The smallest gear in a clock (1), State and government (1), Steering wheel (1), Machine (1), Ship (1), Ship rudder (1), Rope (1), Hospital (1), Cell nucleus (1), Conduct (1) Channel (1), Turtle (1), North star (1), Labyrinth (1), River (1), Maestro (1), Brain in a system (1), Coach (1), Life (1), Sail (1)	25
Administration as a structure that bears responsibility	Puzzle (2), Bee hive (1), Lion (1), Gardener (1), Brain (1), Having children (1), Football team captain (1), Driver (1), Scales (1), Jigsaw puzzle (1)	11
Administration as a strategic structure	Chess (3), Octopus (1), Wave (1), Formula 1 race (1), Architect (1), Mourinho (1), Army (1), Game (1), Plan (1), Singing (1), Lathe machine (1), Arrow that has left the bow (1)	14
Administration as a perpetual structure	Tree (1), Brain (1), Iron (1), Nature (1), Domino (1), Factory (1), Seedling (1), Life-giving process (1), Lego (1), Oxygen (1), Chess (1), Hairclip (1)	12
Administration as a set of rules	Constitution (3), Wheel (2), Family (1), Religion (1), World order (1), Book (1), Queen bee (1), Machine (1), Noah's Ark (1), Baking (1), Puzzle (1), Robot (1), Ivy (1), Traffic rules (1), Cooking (1)	18
Administration as a prestigious structure	Brain (1), Mountain (1), Football team owners (1), Pencil (1), Crystal vase (1), House of Lords (1)	6
Total		174

The participants came up with 130 administration metaphors. The most remarkable ones are brain (9), wheel (6), puzzle (5), power (4), chess (4), tree (3), constitution (3),

mother (3), and domino (3). The concept of "Administration" is also associated with octopus, family, lion, nucleus, factory, cell, mountain, queen bee, crystal vase, robot, maestro, clock, driver, coach, and pyramid.

In Table 2, the metaphors are classified under 11 categories. These categories were created by the researcher. The percentages conveyed by the categories are as follows: Administration as a guiding structure (14,4%), Administration as hierarchical unity and integrity (13,8%), Administration as a significant structure (13,2%), Administration as a structure that solves problems (10,3%), Administration as a set of rules (10,3%), Administration as a strategic structure (8,0%), Administration as an authoritarian structure (7,5%), Administration as a perpetual structure (6,9%), Administration as a structure that bears responsibility (6,3%), Administration as a structure that requires skills and training (5,7%), Administration as a prestigious structure (3,4%).

It can be said that the metaphors that were created by the participants correspond to some basic qualities of administration, such as significance, hierarchy, guidance, and leadership. Some of the opinions expressed by the participants are presented below:

"Administration is like the brain because it is the focal point."

"Administration is like a wheel because it makes other wheels run smoothly when it operates properly."

"Administration is like a plum pit because fruit cannot ripen without its pit."

"Administration is like a cell because a cell contains various parts with various functions."

"Administration is like a machine because a machine makes the whole mechanism run smoothly."

"Administration is like driving because it requires skills and training."

"Administration is like Ankara because it is where authority resides."

"Administration is like a belt because you cannot establish authority unless you tighten the belt."

"Administration is like a channel because it establishes routes and boundaries for a proper education process."

"Administration is like Mourinho because it encourages team play by setting a systematic and well-planned play."

"Administration is like the constitution because it states the rules to follow."

When the perceptions of senior students at Adnan Menderes University, Faculty of Education are examined through metaphors, it is seen that pre-service teachers perceive administration as a rule-based, hierarchical, strategy-based, responsible,

guiding, skill-and-training-based, problem solving, prestigious, and authoritarian structure.

3.7 "School Principal" Metaphors Created by Pre-service Teachers

The metaphors created by Adnan Menderes University, Faculty of Education senior students as a response to the question "School principal is like.....because....." and the categories of metaphors are presented below in Table 3.

Table 3: School Principal Metaphors and Categories

Category	Metaphor	f
Responsible person	Tree branches (1), Mother (1), Soldier (1), Roof of a house (1), Walls of a house (1), King / Authority (1), Leader (1), Ink (1), Brain of a school (1), Pilot (1), Police (1), Clock (1)	12
Shaper	Gardener (2), Tree trunk (1), Fire (1), Mirror (1), Imperative expression of brain (1), Discipline (1), Builder (1), Coffee machine (1), Lamp (1), Mechanical engineer (1), Room (1), Role-Model (1), Water (1), Driver (1), Earth (1), Oil-paint brush (1)	17
Protector	Tree (1), Guard (1), Roof of a house (1), The strongest pillar of a building (1), Seedling (1), Fig tree (1), Ant (1), Shelter (1)	8
Organizer	Commander (2), Tree trunk (1), Octopus (1), Mother (1), Gardener (1), Someone who winds a wheel (1), Landlord (1), Ship rudder (1), Human brain (1), Civil engineer (1), Leader (1), Maestro (1), Marketing manager (1), Puzzle (1), Head waiter (1), Scales (1), Traffic lamp (1), Traffic police (1)	19
Guide	Captain (8), Shepherd (3), Steering wheel (2), Pilot (2), Light bulb (1), İmam (1), DNA (1), Householder (1), Map and compass (1), A worker who canalizes (1), Leader in a flock of birds (1), North star (1), Leader (1), Head waiter (1), Maestro (1), Candle (1), Sultan (1), Headman (1), Clock gears (1), Commissioned officer (1), Driver (1), Team captain (1)	33
Figure of authority	Father (3), Dictator (3), Lion (1), Garbage truck crusher (1), Authority (1), Boss (1)	10
Decision-maker	Father (1), President (1), Alarm clock (1), Grandfather (1), Football referee (1), On/Off switch on a remote control (1), Bus driver (1), Fortress gate (1), Kite (1)	9
Irreplaceable person	Brain (2), Shepherd (2), Core (2), Car engine (1), Flag (1), Backbone (1), Computer motherboard (1), Foundation of a building (1), Roof of a building (1), President (1), Wheel shaft (1), Club Chairman (1), Iron support in a pillar (1), Machine engine (1), Pyramid (1), Thin hair (1), Motherboard (1), Prayer beads head knot (1)	22
Problem solver	Octopus (1), Householder (1), Pointer (1), Parent (1), Lantern (1), Human eye (1), A high-quality eraser (1), Ointment (1), Rubik's cube(1), Traffic police (1)	10
The mediator within the system	Brain (2), Root of a tree (1), Family (1), Tranier (1), Hind wheels (1), Lion (1), Prime Minister (1), Shepherd (1), Aide (1), Climate (1), Captain (1), Classic Approach (1), Queen bee (1), Projector (1), Coach (1)	16
Supervisor	Alarm clock (1), Staff (1), Factory manager (1), Headworker in a factory (1), Pencil (1), Lawperson (1), Coach (1)	7
Strategically-acting person	Enemy (1), Fountain (1), Water (1), Theater actor (1)	4
Laborer	Gardener (4), Messi (1), Earth (1)	6

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Unaffectionate person	Wall (2), Deep freezer (1), Counter-action (1), Bad character (1)	5
Figure of justice	Mother (1), Scales (1), Queen bee (1)	3
Total		181

The participants came up with 133 school principal metaphors. The most remarkable ones are gardener (7), shepherd (6), father (5), brain (4), captain (4), mother (3), pilot (3), leader (3), and dictator (3). The concept of "School principal" is also associated with prime minister, North star, water, climate, alarm clock, commander, queen bee, lamp, Messi, fountain, and ink.

In Table 2, the metaphors are classified under 15 categories. These categories were created by the researcher. The percentages conveyed by the categories are as follows: Guide (18,2%), Irreplaceable person (12,2%), Organizer 10,5%), Shaper (9,4%), The mediator within the system (8,8%), Problem solver (5,5%), Figure of authority (5,5%), Decision-maker (5,0%), Protector (4,4%), Supervisor (3,9%), Laborer (3,3%), Unaffectionate person (2,8%), Strategically-acting person (2,2%), Figure of justice (1,7%).

It can be said that the metaphors that were created by the participants correspond to some basic qualities of school principal, such as decision-maker, problem solver, figure of justice, and supervisor. Some of the opinions expressed by the participants are presented below:

"School principal is like the branches of a tree because they bear the responsibility of fruits and leaves."

"School principal is like a pilot because even a minor distraction can cost them the lives of people."

"School principal is like a builder because they shape the design."

"School principal is like a tree because a strong tree provides shade and happiness."

"School principal is like a leader because they coordinate everything."

"School principal is like the steering wheel because the principal steers the work at school just as the wheel steers the car."

"School principal is like a dictator because they want to control and rule everything."

"School principal is like a grandfather because they make all the decisions."

"School principal is like the head knot of prayer beads because they hold the beads together."

"School principal is like ointment because they detect and heal any deficiency in the system."

"School principal is like climate because they play a crucial role in providing an affirmative atmosphere at schools. They should be neither too tough nor too lenient."

As the perceptions of senior students at Adnan Menderes University, Faculty of Education are examined through metaphors, it is seen that pre-service teachers perceive school principal as a responsible, shape-giving, protective, organizing, guiding, authoritarian, decision-making, problem solving, irreplaceable, supervising, just, and mediating figure.

4. Conclusion, Discussion and Suggestions

The purpose of this study is to present pre-service teachers' perceptions of "administration" and "school principal" reflected through metaphors. The research results demonstrate that pre-service teachers have mostly positive perceptions of administration and school principal concepts – this is an encouraging finding when it is considered that the participants are the potential school administrators of the future. It is also seen that the first three categories with the highest percentages in both "administration" and "school principal" metaphors lists are similar. When pre-service teachers' perception of administration is categorized, the highest frequency (25) is seen in "Administration as a guiding structure" category. In a similar fashion, the highest frequency (33) in "School principal" categorization is seen in "Guide" category. The data show that pre-service teachers' views on administration and school principal concepts are consistent and the participants' perceptions of these two concepts as guiding entities are statistically remarkable. The second category of "Administration" (f=24) is "Administration as hierarchical unity and integrity." The third category of "School principal" (f=19) is "Organizer." This shows that school principals and administration at schools are essential for unity and integrity according to the participants' perceptions.

The third category of "Administration" is "Administration as a significant structure." The second category of "School principal" is "Irreplaceable person." According to the participants' views, both the administration and the school principal represent indispensable elements in an organization. When Adnan Menderes University Faculty of Education senior students' metaphors about school principal and administration are compared, it can be said that the participants' perceptions of administration and school principal comply with one another. Still, pre-service teachers think that administration has more capability to solve problems than school principal. The participants' perceptions of administration manifest a more strategic structure.

According to the research results, administration is perceived to a more authoritarian structure while school principal and administration are considered equal in terms of responsibility. Additionally, administration is perceived to be a structure

that requires skills while there are no school principal metaphors that contain the issue of skills. Therefore, it is safe to state that pre-service teachers perceive administration as a structure that requires skills.

As the studies that focus on different dimension of education are analyzed it can be possible to see many studies that aim to reveal the perceptions through metaphors (Kalyoncu, 2012; Koç, 2014; Koşar, 2016; Sezgin, Koşar, Koşar ve Er, 2017 vb.). There are a number of studies in literature that convey similar results. In a study titled "A Study of Metaphor Based on Pre-service Pre-school Teachers' Perceptions of School Administrator" and conducted by Zembat, Tunçeli, and Akşin (2015), the categories of metaphors show that the first three categories with highest percentages are "guiding" (23,076%), "organizing" (16,153%), and "focus of administration" (11,538%). Similarly, in this study the first three categories are "Guide" (18,2%), "Irreplaceable" (12,2%), and "Organizer" (10,5%). Although the categories in similar metaphor studies on the concepts of school administrator and school principal are named differently, the metaphors within the three abovementioned categories are similar (Yalçın and Erginer, 2012; Dönmez 2008; Cerit, 2008).

In Çobanoğlu's and Gökalp's study titled "Pre-service Teachers' Perceptions of School Principal" (2015), it is seen that the most recurring metaphors of school principal are father, lion, shepherd, dictator, and mother. These findings show complete parallelism with the ones in our study because the metaphors with the highest frequency levels in our study are gardener, shepherd, father, captain, dictator, mother, lion, and leader. Therefore, the perceptions of the school principal by the students at Rize Recep Tayyip Edoğan University Faculty of Education, Department of Religious Culture and Ethics in the academic year 2013-2014 are parallel to the perceptions of pre-service teachers at Adnan Menderes University Faculty of Education.

It is observed by this study that the rate of negative metaphors about school principals is very low (8,9%). In a comprehensive study titled "Perceptions of the School Principal Reflected through Metaphors at Primary Schools" by Yalçın and Enginer (2012), the rate of negative metaphors is high (22%). The reason for such a high rate is thought to be the choice of sampling. Yalçın and Enginer (2012) included the students, teachers, and parents in their study and this might have affected the results. Also, the reason for the highest percentage of "Protection" metaphors might be the fact that the study was conducted at primary schools. This study does not agree with Yalçın and Enginer's research results and maintain low rates for the "Protection" category. This disagreement may be indicating that school principals are perceived to be more protective at primary schools.

In a study by Pesen, İdris and Gedik (2015) titled "The Perceptions of Principal by Sophomore Students at Child Development Department", 80 students were asked to answer questions about the school principals at the schools where these students interned. The results of this study agree with the ones in Yalçın and Enginer's (2012) study, but differ from the ones in our study. When one considers that the abovementioned 80 child development students interned at kindergartens, pre-school classes, and primary schools, it is understood that the school principal metaphors they created tended to be negative. Therefore, it is deduced that the teachers who work at kindergartens, pre-school classes, and primary schools are more likely to develop a negative perception of school principals as opposed to the ones who work at higher education institutions.

In a study by Gelmez and Çetin (2012) titled "The Perceptions of School Administration Reflected through the Metaphors by Teachers and Administrators (District of Beyoğlu, İstanbul Case)" the researchers investigated how teachers and administrators at primary schools in Beyoğlu perceived school administration. The study found that these teachers and administrators perceived school administration as a unifying element. Therefore, the results of Gelmez and Çetin's study agree with those of our study.

Günbayı (2011) examines the metaphors used by school principals when defining school administration and comes up with 6 categories. These metaphors are octopus, horse, bee, book, seesaw, boxer, football team, steam machine, wrist watch, rocket, robot, computer, sun, tree, and garden. By these metaphors, the participants emphasized some certain characteristics such as coherence, team-work, hierarchy and its consequences, the difficulty of using power and authority due to the central structure of Turkish education system (Örücü, 2014). The results of the study by Günbayı (2012) are largely parallel to the results in our study.

In a study titled "Pre-service Teachers' Perceptions of School Administrator Reflected through Metaphors" by Kösterelioğlu (2014) shows that 232 junior and senior students at Amasya University Faculty of Education in the academic year 2012-2013 spring term have created 60 metaphors about the concept of school administrator. These metaphors were classified under 21 categories. The highest rates of frequency (guide and facilitator, center of administration, and irreplaceable) in three categories indicate a parallelism to our study.

The research by Çakıcı and İslamoğlu (2012), titled "An Analysis of Academics' Perceptions of Faculty and College Administrators Reflected through Metaphors", lists a number of metaphors, both positive and negative, about the administrative methods and approaches. It has been observed that the participants tend to create affirmative

metaphors about administrators. The results also indicate a participative and democratic administration system. Çakıcı and İslamoğlu's study is significant in terms of developing a comparison between the perceptions of administration in primary and secondary schools and administration at universities. In a similar fashion, Tüzel and Şahin (2014) investigate primary school 1st grade students' perceptions of school administrators through the pictures they draw and the metaphors they create. In order to avoid misinterpretation, the students were asked to provide short explanations for their pictures. It is seen that most students came up with affirmative metaphors such as flower, sun, and tree. School principals and deputies are perceived to be secluded figures – spending most of their time in their offices, staying away from the school corridors, and appearing only in the special ceremonies. When our study, which investigates school principal perceptions of pre-service teachers at Adnan Menderes University Faculty of Education, is compared to Tüzel and Şahin's study, it is seen that the results of two studies differ drastically. It is safe to say that the age of participants is a significant determinant in a research.

In line with results of the study, certain suggestions can be offered. In order to maintain pre-service teachers' affirmative perception, to reduce negative perception to a minimum, and to create awareness, the number of school administration and leadership courses can be increased in bachelor programs. It is suggested that school administration practices are added to the content of school experience courses. Also, a long-term study can be conducted to investigate how and in what aspects pre-service teachers' perceptions of "school principal" and "administration" change after graduation for a significant contribution to the literature. Because school principals are able to shape teachers' perceptions by means of their attitudes, they should remember that the more attention they pay to the impression created on new teachers, the better impacts they can have on institutions and education.

References

1. Aydın, M., (2015). *Eğitim Yönetimi*, Ankara: Gazi Kitabevi Tic. Ltd. Şti.
2. Balcı, A. (2008). Türkiye'de eğitim yönetiminin bilimleşme düzeyi. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 14 (2), 181-209.
3. Balcı, A. ve Apaydın, Ç. (2009). Türkiye'de eğitim yönetimi araştırmalarının durumu: Kuram ve uygulamada eğitim yönetimi dergisi örneği. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 15 (59), 325-343.
4. Başaran, İ. E., (1993). *Türkiye Eğitim Sistem*. Ankara: Gül Yayınevi.

5. Cemaloğlu, N. (2005). Türkiye'de okul yöneticisi yetiştirme ve istihdamı: Varolan durum, gelecekteki olası gelişmeler ve sorunlar. *Gazi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 25 (2), 249-274.
6. Cerit, Y. (2008). Öğrenci, öğretmen ve yöneticilerin müdür kavramı ile ilgili metaforlara ilişkin görüşleri. *Eğitim ve Bilim*, 33 (147), 3-13.
7. Çakıcı, A. ve İslamoğlu, A.E. (2012). Akademisyenlerin fakülte ve yükseköğretim yöneticilerine ilişkin algılarının metaforlarla analizi. *Çağ Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 9(2), 77-99.
8. Çobanoğlu, N. ve Gökalp, S. (2015). Öğretmen adaylarının okul müdürüne ilişkin algıları. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 12 (31), 279-295.
9. Dönmez, Ö. (2008). *Türk eğitim sisteminde kullanılan yönetici metaforları (Kayseri ili örneği)*. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Erciyes Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
10. Gelmez Ş. ve Çetin, M. H. (2012). Öğretmen ve okul yöneticilerin metaforlar vasıtasıyla okul yönetimi algıları (İstanbul Beyoğlu ilçesi örneği)". <https://dosyalar.nevsehir.edu.tr> 02.06.2017 tarihinde indirilmiştir
11. Goldstein, L.B. (2005). Becoming a teacher as a hero's journey: using metaphor in preservice teacher education. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 32 (1), 7-24.
12. Günbayı, İ. (2011). Principals' perceptions on school management: A case study with metaphorical Analysis. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 3(2), 541-561.
13. Kalyoncu, R. (2012). Görsel sanatlar öğretmeni adaylarının "öğretmenlik" kavramına ilişkin metaforları. *Mustafa Kemal Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 9 (20), 471-484.
14. Koç, E. S. (2014). Sınıf öğretmeni adaylarının öğretmen ve öğretmenlik mesleği kavramlarına ilişkin metaforik algıları. *İnönü Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 15 (1), 47-72.
15. Koşar, D. (2016). Öğretmen adaylarının üniversite ve öğretim elemanı kavramlarına ilişkin metaforik algıları. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 8 (3), 113-127.
16. Kösterelioğlu, M.A., (2014). Öğretmen adaylarının okul yöneticisi kavramına ilişkin metaforik algıları. *Zeitschrift für die Welt der Türken Journal of World of Turks (ZfWT)*, 6 (3), 115-133.
17. Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

18. Morgan, G. (1998). *Yönetim ve Örgüt Teorilerinde Metafor*. (Çev: G. Bulut). İstanbul: MESS Yayınları.
19. Örucü, D. ve Şimşek, H. (2011). Akademisyenlerin gözünden Türkiye'de eğitim yönetiminin akademik durumu: nitel bir analiz. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 17 (2), 167-197.
20. Örucü, D. (2014). Öğretmen adaylarının okul, okul yönetimi ve Türk eğitim sistemine yönelik metaforik algıları. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 20 (3), 327-358.
21. Pesen, A., Kara, İ. ve Gedik, M. (2015) Çocuk gelişimi bölümü 2. sınıf öğrencilerinin "müdür" kavramına ilişkin metafor algıları. *Siirt Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 5: 28-48.
22. Resmi Gazete (2014). Yayın Tarihi: Haziran, 2014. Sayısı: 29026
23. Resmi Gazete (2015). Yayın Tarihi: Ekim, 2015. Sayısı: 29494.
24. Saban, A., Koçbeker, B. N. ve Saban, A. (2006). Öğretmen adaylarının öğretmen kavramına ilişkin algılarının metafor analizi yoluyla incelenmesi. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimleri*, 6(2), 461-522.
25. Sezgin, F.; Koşar, D.; Koşar, S. ve Er, E. (2017). Öğretmenlerin öğrenciye yönelik metaforlarının belirlenmesine ilişkin nitel bir araştırma. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 32 (3), 600-611.
26. Tüzel, E. ve Şahin, D. (2014). İlköğretim birinci kademe öğrencilerinin okul yöneticilerine ilişkin metaforları. *Adıyaman Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 7 (17), 355-396.
27. Yalçın, M. ve Erginer, A. (2012). İlköğretim okullarında okul müdürüne ilişkin metaforik algıları. *Öğretmen Eğitimi ve Eğitimcileri Dergisi*, 1 (2), 229-256.
28. Yıldırım, A.ve Şimşek, H (2008). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri*, Ankara: Seçkin Yayınları.
29. Zembat, H.; Tunçeli, H.İ. ve Akşin, E. (2015). Okulöncesi öğretmenlerin adaylarının "okul yöneticisi" kavramına ilişkin algılarına yönelik metafor çalışması. *Hacettepe University Faculty of Health Science Journal*, 1 (2), 446-459.

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REFLECTED THROUGH METAPHORS

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